

LEARNING STYLES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT The investigator aimed to find out the significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students. The investigator used Learning style scale. The investigator got marks of half-yearly examination in all the subjects from the high school students and used as the scores of academic achievement. The investigator used stratified random sampling technique. Ten schools were selected randomly from Sankarankovil Taluk. From those schools 300 high school students were randomly selected as sample. The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyze the data. From the result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students.

KEYWORDS : Learning Style, Academic Achievement, Correlation, Stratified random sampling

INTRODUCTION

Learning is something that takes place inside a person's heads in the brain and it is an enormously intricate and complex process. Knowledge about learning can be accumulated by scientific methods when such knowledge is adequately verified, it can be expressed as learning principles. Learning is a process, which enables the teacher to recognize that learning has taken place when they note a behavioural change in the learner and also when they note the persistence of this change. Learning styles are simply approaches or ways of learning. Psychologists, academics and other theoreticians have developed any number of ideas and theories about the way people learn. Educationalists have used these theories about the way people pedagogies, which are aimed at allowing children to be more effective and efficient learners. To make these strategies effective. They must be simple, easy to implement in a wide variety of contexts, with children of different ages across a variety of different subject areas and with different learning environments. Most of all teachers need to have some idea of why they are using the strategies in the first place. According to James and Gardener (1995), "Learning style is defined as "the complex manner in which and conditions under which learners most efficiently and most effectively perceive process, store and recall what they are attempting to learn" "Learning styles is the way individuals concentrate on absorb and retain new of difficult materials or skills. An individual's learning style is the way that person begins to process, internalize and concentrate one material.

It refers to the knowledge attained or skill developed in school subject usually designated by test scores or by marks assigned by teachers or by both. Evaluation of learning outcomes of the students by measuring their academic achievement has been in practice for a long time. One the basis of Academic achievement, the appropriateness of the methods of imparting knowledge may be judged. In the present socio-economic and cultural context Academic achievement is of paramount importance and schools place great emphasis on it. Progress in future to a great extent depends upon the academic attainment of the students. At all school level there exist enormous differences in the Academic attainment of students ranging from high to low. Academic achievement which means the proficiency of performance in a given subject or body of knowledge helps in declaring the examinee successful or unsuccessful, choosing students for various professional and Academic courses and selecting candidates for different jobs.

SIGNIFICANCE FOR THE STUDY

A learning style is a student's consistent way of responding to and using stimuli in the context of learning. "Learning style" is generally used to explain an individual's natural or habitual pattern of acquiring and processing information in learning situations. Learning styles is an important factor in the Academic achievement of the students. Some students have good learning styles, some students may have poor learning styles which may be due to several factors such as family backgrounds, economic status, size of the family, education of the

parents. Individual differences also play a vital role in learning styles of children. Learning styles may be different from child to child and they also differ in case of high, average and low achievers. And the learning styles also vary among the students from school to school, management to management, locality-to-locality. In our present societal setup, school serves as one major instrument in imparting knowledge. It has become mandatory and obligation for the parents and the government to provide education to all children in our nation. In this scenario no child is entitled to lose the privilege of studying in a school. All school entrants, from beginning to end, require some styles and practice them to successfully pursue knowledge. These possessed learning styles play a vital role in deciding their level of achievement. These achieved test score determines their future career. The ambitions and aspirations of our students are largely governed by their learning skills adopted by the students. Kothari commission states, at the out set, the destiny of a nation is shaped in classrooms. If such a weightage is given to students, how much more weightage should be given to their learning styles. Individual differences play an important role in academic achievement of students. There have been many attempts to address the problem of low academic achievement and some factors have been identified in explaining academic achievement. Research on learning style demonstrates that individuals differ in their learning style and that no single delivery system is optimal for all students. Students who fail to adapt to a new instructional context may also face academic difficulties. So the investigator is brimmed with the zest to know whether there is any significant relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of high schools students.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out the significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students.

TOOLS USED

Learning style scale: It is validated and standardized by the investigator (2016).

Academic Achievement: The investigator got marks of half-yearly examination in all the subjects from the high school students.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population for the present study was all the IX and X standard high school students in the schools of Sankarankovil Taluk.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The investigator used stratified random sampling technique. Ten schools were selected randomly from Sankarankovil Taluk. From those schools 300 high school students were randomly selected as sample.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyze the data.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

There is no significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students.

Table – 1

Pearson correlation analysis showing the relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students

Correlation	Calculated value of ""	N	Table of value ""	Remarks At 5% level
Learning style and academic achievement	0.231	300	0.113	S

It is inferred from the above table that the -value (0.231) is greater than the calculated value for df (299) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students.

FINDING AND INTERPRETATION

From the result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students. If students can be enabled to be more aware of themselves and the ways in which they are likely to achieve better, they can be encouraged to develop more effective and more flexible learning styles. On the other hand, two major strategies have been proposed for enhancing students' achievement. One is through providing learning environments that match students' learning styles. The second strategy is through teaching for a balanced use of styles or flexibility.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The present study showed that there is relationship between learning style and academic achievement of high school students. From this we can conclude that lack of aware on learning style contributes to poor academic achievement and vice versa. Steps should therefore be taken by parents, caretakers, and teachers to understand the importance of learning style of children.
- The teachers may find out own preferred learning style which often becomes predominant learning style. Teacher may find out students learning style for better learning.
- Parents should be made aware about different kind of approaches help their child learn best.
- Educational psychologists need to develop insights into the specific learning styles which are favored by the educational system

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